

Management

RESEARCH ON MARKETING OF PRODUCTS AT KODAIKANAL TOURISM CENTRE – DINDIGUL DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The study intends to find answers to the problems and shortcomings in tourism infrastructure development in the study area and tourism support services such as quantity and quality of public transport, accommodation, food, bank, park facility, shopping, medical facilities and so on. The opinion of and suggestions from the tourist respondents incorporated herein would provide guidelines for future course of action to be followed in Kodaikanal.

Keywords:

Tourism, economic development, foreign exchange & Kodaikanal.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism plays a vital role in the economic development, because it is the second largest sector for earning foreign exchange. It generates substantial economic benefits to both the host and home countries. The main economic impact of tourism includes its contribution to government revenues, generation of foreign exchange earnings and employment creation along with the initiation of various business opportunities. In this context Kodaikanal is the main place which has high potentials for tourism and allied activities. The present study analyses the marketing of tourism products in Kodaikanal from the views of tourists.

2. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The main aim of the study is to analyse the satisfaction of the tourists towards tourism facilities available in Kodaikanal. The study intends to find answers to the problems and shortcomings in tourism infrastructure development in the study area and tourism support services such as quantity and quality of public transport, accommodation, food, bank, park facility, shopping,

medical facilities and so on. The opinion of and suggestions from the tourist respondents incorporated herein would provide guidelines for future course of action to be followed in Kodaikanal.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following objectives have been framed for the study.

- 1) To study the socio economic background and the expenditure pattern of the tourists.
- 2) To study the attitudes of tourists towards marketing of tourism products in Kodaikanal at Dindigul district.
- 3) To find out the relationship between satisfaction and socio economic background of tourists in Kodaikanal at Dindigul district.
- 4) To suggest a few measures for the betterment of marketing of tourism products in Kodaikanal at Dindigul district.

4. METHODOLOGY

The present study is based on both primary and secondary data. Tourists have been visiting various places of Kodaikanal at Dindigul district. The researcher collected the primary data from tourists visiting various places of Kodaikanal at Dindigul district. For the collection of primary data, 50 tourists were selected through convenient sampling method. They were met at their hotels or guest houses where they were residing. A well-structured interview schedule was adopted to collect the primary data.

Table 1: Gender wise distribution of tourists

Sl. No	Gender	No. of Tourists	Percentage
1	Male	36	72
2	Female	16	32
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

The above table reveals that out of 50 tourists, 72 per cent of the tourists are male and the remaining 32 per cent of the tourists are female. It is evident from table that majority of the tourists are male.

Table 2: Age wise distribution of tourists

Sl. No	Age	No. of Tourists	Percentage
1	Below 20	6	12
2	21 to 30	17	34
3	31 to 40	18	36
4	41 to 50	7	14
5	Above 50	2	4
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 3: Marital Status wise distribution of tourists

Sl. No	Marital Status	No. of Tourists	Percentage
1	Married	31	70
2	Unmarried	15	30
3	Widow	04	8
	Total	500	100

Source: Primary data

Table 3 reveals that 70 per cent of the tourists are married, 30 per cent of the tourists

Table 4: Occupation wise distribution of tourists

Si. No	Occupation	No. of Tourists	Percentage
1	Business	12	24
2	Government employees	12	24
3	Private employees	9	18
4	Students	4	8
5	Agriculturists	6	12
6	Professionals	7	14
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Table 5 pictures the occupational status of tourists who were visiting Kodaikanal. It is clear from table that 24 per cent of the tourists were government employees, another 24 per cent of the tourists were businessmen, 18 per cent of the tourists were private employees, 14 per cent of the tourists were professionals, 12 per cent are agriculturist and 8 per cent of the respondents are students.

5. FINDINGS & SUGGESTIONS

- Kodaikanal is an ancient tourist place offering scope for a lot of tourism and business activities. The approach needed for Kodaikanal is of course much different from that of other places. A metro oriented tourism activity may be planned and executed in the city.
- Cleanliness is another problem in the tourist spots. Tourists should avoid throwing wastes in the tourist spots. This will spoil the entire tourist area and in a long run people may avoid the particular tourist spot in their tour programme. Tourists must co-operate in maintaining cleanliness in the tourist spots.
- Regarding the beautification, maintaining, and cleanliness of the city the local administration should concentrate on cleaning and widening the paths and roads and maintaining and setting up of underground drainage system for the whole town can change the city as pollution free city.

6. CONCLUSION

Kodaikanal is one of the important tourist spots with all potentials to attract tourists, but it is not fully explored and utilized. Some tourists visited Kodaikanal more than one times. But some tourists stated that nothing is being done artificially to attract tourist except the nature attractions.

In this situation the government should take steps to develop the infrastructure facilities and create man-made attractions. Kodaikanal is a unique location and a good tourist point. Therefore, the govef the tourists were agriculturists and 8 per cent of the tourists were students meaning 8 per cent of the tourists are widow. It is clear from table that majority of the tourists are married.

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